

CryptoSecurity Consultant

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Abstract

Keywords:

1. Introduction

In the newly developing market of cryptocurrencies, the need to securely store and protect assets is of critical importance. Security Sense focuses on implementing security solutions and infrastructure for the custody of digital assets while minimizing attack surface.

2. Aim

To prepare and educate crypto hedge funds, family offices, and high net worth individuals about the importance and value of self-custodianship as well as proper cold storage.

3. Material and methods

A focus on deep cold storage techniques using the newest available technology while also focusing on educating the client-base on how to navigate their crypto funds in a safe and secure environment.

4. Results

Evaluate and asses areas of improvement including operational and physical security functionality of methods within the crypto space.

5. Conclusions

Crypto security is at the forefront of cryptocurrency custodianship. New techniques are developed and implemented to keep your digital assets safe from malicious actors. Adoption of these practices will inherently make the cryptocurrency universe a safer place to carry out business and personal matters. Therefore, it is vital for acceptance of these key basic principals to secure digital funds.

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6. Keywords

Cryptocurrency; Bitcoin; Ethereum; Cryptography; Security; Network Security; Operational Security; CryptoSecurity

Author biography

Joshua Stinson is the Founder and Chief Security Officer of Security Sense LLC, a leading cryptocurrency security & cold storage provisions. He has a deep background in computer science and cryptography, with over 7 years experience implementing security solutions. Josh focuses his practice on helping digital asset funds reduce their attack surface area, and maintain obscurity. He implements a holistic suite of best in class security practices including cold storage custodianship, multi-signature authorization, redundancy controls, efficient private key storage, encrypted networks/ communications as well as physical and operational security best practices